

**UNIVERSITY OF MAIDUGURI
COLLEGE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES**

**ASSESSMENT OF WORKPLACE BURNOUT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN
PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTERS IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE.**

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DEDICATION

We dedicate this work to God Almighty for His bounties and mercies and to our parents/ guardians for their relentless support, encouragement and prayers.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

	PAGE
DEDICATION	i
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.....	ii
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	iv
LIST OF FIGURES	v
ABSTRACT.....	vi
CHAPTERS	
INTRODUCTION.....	1
LITERATURE REVIEW.....	5
MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY.....	10
OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSION.....	16
SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION.....	47
LIST OF REFERENCES.....	51
APPENDICES	
A. QUESTIONNAIRE.....	54
B. INFORMED CONSENT FORM.....	58
C. ETHICAL CLEARANCE.....	59
D. CALCULATION OF SAMPLE INTERVAL.....	60

LIST OF TABLES

	PAGE
1. Socio-demographic Characteristics of Healthcare Workers in Primary Health Care Centres in Maiduguri, Borno State, July 2025.....	18
2. Burnout Assessment Among Healthcare Workers in Primary Health Care Centers in Maiduguri, Borno State, July 2025.....	22
3. Coping Mechanisms Adopted by Health Care workers in Primary Health Care Centers to Manage Burnout in Maiduguri, Borno State, July 2025.....	35
4. Work Related Factors of Healthcare Workers on Prevalence of Workplace Burnout in Primary Health Care Centers in Maiduguri, Borno State, July 2025.....	41
5. Factors Associated with Socio-Demographic Variables and Level of Workplace Burnout Among Primary Healthcare Workers in Primary Health Care Centers in Maiduguri, Borno State, July 2025.....	43

LIST OF FIGURES

	PAGE
1. Burnout Level of Healthcare Workers in Primary Health Care Centers in Jere and MMC LGA, Borno State.....	33

ABSTRACT

Burnout among Healthcare Workers (HCWs) threatens workforce sustainability and patient safety, particularly in resource constrained and conflict affected settings like Maiduguri. This study aims to assess workplace burnout, coping mechanisms, and associated factors among HCWs in Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri, Borno State. A descriptive cross-sectional study design was employed across 7 PHCs selected via multistage sampling in Jere and MMC LGAs. Data was collected using a semi structured, pretested, interviewer administered questionnaire, and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods. A total of 272 questionnaires were administered, of which all were validly completed (response rate of 100%). Associations were explored with chi-square/Fisher's exact tests ($p \leq 0.05$).

The findings revealed that Participants were predominantly female (65.1%), mean age 33.85 ± 9.03 years, CHEWs formed the largest cadre (37.5%). Most of the respondent worked 10–16 hours/day (87.5%). Burnout levels were divided into low, moderate and high categories. Burnout levels were low in 29 (10.7%), moderate in 125 (46%), and high in 118 (43.4%). The sociodemographic factor significantly associated with burnout was years of work experience ($\chi^2=19.167$, $p=0.004$) and work days per week ($\chi^2=5.735$, $p=0.044$). Common coping mechanisms used by the PHC workers to overcome burnout included prayer/religious support, time management, rest breaks, while substance use was rare.

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

A significant challenge confronting global healthcare systems, patient care and safety is the issue of burnout among Healthcare Workers (HCWs) (1). Burnout is characterized by physical and emotional exhaustion from long term exposure to emotionally demanding work. Burnout affects interpersonal skills, job performance, career satisfaction and psychological health (2). The World Health Organization (WHO) in the 11th Revision of international Classification of diseases classified burnout as an "Occupational phenomenon" and not just a medical condition, attributing it to unmanaged chronic workplace stress. The consequences of burnout are numerous, affecting both organizations and individuals through increased absenteeism, workplace accidents, reduced productivity and conflicts. Healthcare professionals (HCPs) are particularly vulnerable due to the demanding nature of their work, long shifts and high-stress environments (3,4). Contributing factors include staff shortages, extended work hours, poor leadership, lack of social support, interpersonal conflicts and personal life stressors. World Health Organization (WHO) emphasized the importance of robust Primary Health Care (PHC) in achieving universal health coverage (5,6).

Primary Health Care is defined as an essential healthcare based on practical, scientifically sound and socially acceptable methods and technology, made universally accessible to individuals and families in the community through their full participation and at a cost

that the individual and community can afford (7). In Nigeria, PHC workers endure significant challenges, particularly in conflict afflicted zones like Borno State (8).

The WHO 2019 HeRAMS (Health Resources and Services availability monitoring system) assessments revealed that 27 Per cent of health facilities in Borno State were fully destroyed, while 14 per cent were partially damaged. Specifically, 16 per cent and 11 Per cent of PHC centers were partially and completely damaged respectively, with severe shortage of staff, medications, water and infection control supplies (8). The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated burnout, with a global prevalence of 52 Per cent among Health Care Workers (9). In India, 26.9 Per cent of Healthcare workers experienced work related burnout, especially among doctors and support staff (10). A recent study in found 85 Per cent burnout rate among Health Care Workers in private hospitals in Abuja (11). Similarly, research in Delta State identified workload 30.7 per cent and work shift 20.0 per cent as key contributors to burnout, with an overall burnout prevalence of 45 Per cent (1). Specifically, in Maiduguri a study reported a 21.5 Per cent burnout rate among clinical staff in tertiary hospitals, with high levels of emotional exhaustion 77.4 Per cent and depression 10.7 Per cent (12). Primary Health Care workers play a foundational role in Nigeria's healthcare system, understanding burnout prevalence, coping mechanisms and factors associated with burnout in this group is essential (8).

Statement of the Problem

Burnout is of significant public health concern due to its physical, mental and occupational health consequences including headache, sleep disturbances, reduced productivity and poor quality of life. It is highly associated with numerous psychiatric disorders including

depression, anxiety, substance abuse and suicidal tendency among healthcare workers (2). Health care professionals may develop symptoms such as, irritability, mood swings, insomnia, and a sense of failure as a consequence of burnout, these symptoms may ultimately lead to decreased job performance and poor patient care (4). It not only compromises the mental and physical health of health care workers but also increases the rate at which staff leave and are replaced at work place, promote absenteeism and likelihood of medical errors and inefficient patient care (4). In Borno State, Primary Health Care workers operate under extreme stress due to persistent insecurity in the region. This is compounded by severe resource shortages, understaffing and unsustainable workloads, all of which have significantly increased burnout among this group of healthcare workforce (8).

Justification of the Study

There is limited study on burnout among Primary Health Care workers in Maiduguri, despite their critical role in delivering care amidst insecurity and resource constraints. Most studies among healthcare professionals have focused on tertiary healthcare workers leaving the Primary Health Care workers grossly under studied (11, 12). This study, therefore aims to fill the gap and address a pressing but overlooked problem by assessing the prevalence of burnout, exploring the coping mechanisms and identifying key factors associated with burnout in PHC workers in Maiduguri, Borno state.

Significance of the Study

The findings from this research will help improve Primary Health Care service delivery in Maiduguri by guiding policy makers, partner organizations and health administrators in designing effective interventions and policies aimed at reducing burnout, improve wellbeing and productivity of healthcare workers.

Objectives of the Study

General Objective

To assess workplace burnout among Healthcare workers in Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri, Borno State.

Specific Objectives

1. To determine the level of burnout among healthcare workers in Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri, Borno State.
2. To determine the coping mechanisms used to overcome burnout by healthcare workers in Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri, Borno State.
3. To determine work related factors of healthcare workers on workplace burnout in Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri, Borno State.
4. To evaluate factors associated with socio-demographic characteristics and the level of workplace burnout.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction

Burnout is a mental and emotional condition that happens when someone is under constant stress at work. It includes feeling emotionally drained, becoming distant or negative about the job and feeling like one is not achieving much (13). The healthcare sector is especially affected because of emotionally demanding patient care, long working hours, pressure to make critical decisions and limited resources (14). In low- and middle-income countries like Nigeria, additional stressors such as low pay, inadequate infrastructure and a growing workload worsened by migration of healthcare workers increases the level of burnout among healthcare workers (15). This results in a situation where health workers face high job demands but have very limited support and resources. Assessing the prevalence of burnout and its effect, is essential for creating solutions that protect healthcare workers well-being, lower the risk of medical errors and enhance patient care worldwide (16).

Level of Burnout among Healthcare workers

Multiple studies have documented the prevalence of burnout among healthcare workers in various health care settings. Burnout is prevalent among Primary Health Care workers, with studies reporting varying rates. In Iran, 52.9 Per cent of Primary Health Care staff suffered from high burnout while the rate is 7 Per cent in Brazil's PHC staff (17). In Finland, the prevalence of burnout among healthcare workers is among the lowest reported in Europe, with 4.3 Per cent of staff experiencing high burnout in a multinational

survey, compared to 20.6 Per cent in Slovenia and 25 Per cent in Turkey (18). In India, Studies have found that 26.9 Per cent of healthcare workers experienced work related burnout, especially among doctors and support staff (10). The 2020 Medscape National Physician Burnout and Suicide Report shows a burnout rate of about 43 Per cent, which remains quite similar to the 46 Per cent reported in 2015 and 39.8 Per cent in 2013 (18). A study conducted across five tertiary hospitals in Nigeria found that 75.5 Per cent of doctors experienced burnout, with higher levels of exhaustion linked to years of clinical experience (16). Studies in Abuja found an 85 Per cent burnout rate among Health Care Workers in private hospitals (11). Similarly, research in Delta State identified workload 30.7Per cent and shift work 20 Per cent as key contributors to burnout, with an overall burnout prevalence of 45 Per cent (1). During the COVID-19 pandemic, doctors in Lagos reported 62.2 Per cent personal burnout and 52.2 Per cent work-related burnout, mainly due to working over 71 hours per week and being in close contact with COVID-19 patients (15). Nurses at a tertiary hospital in Enugu showed higher burnout rates 78.1 Per cent compared to doctors. Among them, 53.8 Per cent felt a reduced sense of achievement, and 47.6 Per cent experienced emotional detachment (14).

In Maiduguri, a study reported a 21.5 Per cent burnout rate among clinical staff in tertiary hospitals, with high levels of emotional exhaustion 77.4 Per cent and depression 10.7Per cent (12). Healthcare worker burnout is mainly assessed using standardized tools, with the Maslach, Copenhagen and Oldenburg burnout inventory, although in clinical research, the Oldenburg burnout Inventory has gained prominence due to its applicability. It assesses burnout in two core domains, Exhaustion which is physical, emotional, and

cognitive fatigue and Disengagement which is distancing oneself from one's work and developing doubts (19).

Coping mechanisms to overcome burnout

Burnout among healthcare workers has been widely studied, particularly the aspect of stress and coping mechanisms. One of the most significant frameworks is the transactional Model of Stress and Coping developed by Lazarus and Folkman (20). According to this model, coping is a dynamic process that involves cognitive and behavioral efforts to manage internal or external demands that are perceived as taxing or exceeding the individual's resources (20). This model classifies coping into two main strategies: problem focused coping and emotion focused coping. Problem focused coping aims to address the source of stress directly through strategies like seeking help, restructuring duties, or negotiating workload. In contrast, emotion-focused coping targets the regulation of the emotional distress associated with the stressor, such as through avoidance, prayer, venting, or substance use (20).

The effectiveness of these strategies can vary. A study among healthcare workers in Belgium, reported that 34 Per cent of respondents used religious support to manage stress, indicating a common reliance on emotion-focused coping (18). A systematic review during the COVID-19 pandemic found that avoidant behavior, a form of emotion-focused coping, seems to be ineffective in preventing burnout and can worsen it when the stressor cannot be removed from the work environment (21).

In the Nigerian studies, specific coping behaviors have been identified. For instance, over 51 Per cent of nurses (n=121) in a study in Enugu reported overeating at work as a way to cope with stress (14). Other adaptive measures, such as flexible scheduled rest breaks during work hours, can promote a healthier work-life balance, allowing healthcare workers to recover from fatigue and avoid long-term exhaustion (22). A study among 150 healthcare at Federal Medical Center Ondo found that 24 (16%) adopt a lot of positive reframing followed by 17 (11.3%) of religion, 16 (10.7%) of informational support and 13 (8.7%) of acceptance as coping strategy. Furthermore, 44.7 Per cent of the respondents adopt a little bit of emotional support, followed by self-distraction (44%), humor (42%) and informational support (38%). However, the least adopted coping strategies among the respondents were substance use (92%) (23).

Factors associated with burnout among Healthcare workers

Factors associated with burnout include sociodemographic factors such as age, gender, marital status, work experience, cadre and other work related factors such as work shifts long working hours and workload (7,17). A study in Saudi Arabia found that personal and work-related burnout scores were significantly higher among female healthcare workers, those working in rotating day-and-night shifts, those working more than 55 hours per week (24). The study in Finland shows that burnout increase only slightly with age, with younger healthcare workers reporting more of emotional exhaustion due to limited experience and heavy workloads. In terms of gender, Female nurses face additional burnout from balancing professional responsibilities with domestic obligations. A cross-sectional study conducted among Nigerian nurses in tertiary health institutions

documented high levels of burnout and psychological distress. Among 210 respondents, 43 Per cent reported high emotional exhaustion, 47 Per cent experienced high depersonalization and 54 Per cent felt reduced personal accomplishment (18, 26). In 2015, data from the Medscape National Physician Report indicate that women physicians reported burnout (51% female vs 43% male and in 2020, 48% female vs 37% male). Among healthcare professionals, nurses showed high levels of occupational exhaustion, with 14.3 Per cent experiencing depersonalization, while this figure was 25 Per cent among doctors. Among Spanish primary healthcare nurses, 40.24 Per cent had high burnout levels (7). Feelings of low personal accomplishment were common across different healthcare workers with 57.1 Per cent in doctors, 45 Per cent in nurses, and 75 Per cent in allied health workers (25). Work related factors such as shift work, workload, role clarity, and ambiguity are leading causes of burnout among healthcare workers. A study Among Nigerian nurses found burnout to be primarily driven by excessive workloads, high nurse patient ratios, and prolonged working hours without rest (26).

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

Locale

This study was conducted in Maiduguri, the capital city of Borno State, one of the oldest cities in Nigeria situated in the North Eastern part of the country. Maiduguri is situated between latitude 11°N and 15°N and longitude 10°E to 25°E. The land area of Maiduguri is 30355sq.km with a population of about 802988 people according to national census 2006. Its climate is harsh with temperature range of 32° to 42°. Maiduguri has a rich cultural heritage and is pluralistic in ethnic composition with Kanuri being the predominant spoken language. Most of the inhabitants are Muslims with fewer Christians and traditionalists (27).

The research specifically focuses on Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) situated within Maiduguri, Borno State which include Jere and Maiduguri Metropolitan Council (MMC) Local Government Areas. These LGAs are the most urbanized and densely populated areas in Borno State, serving as administrative, commercial and healthcare hubs. Borno State host about 85 functional PHCs that provide essential services such as maternal and child healthcare, immunization, outpatient consultations and public health education (8). Due to their central role in the delivery of Primary Health Care services and their accessibility, these areas were considered appropriate for assessing workplace burnout among healthcare workers. Additionally, the region has experienced prolonged exposure to conflict and displacement, which may further influence the stress levels and workload of healthcare professionals operating in these settings.

Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional study.

Study Population

Healthcare workers in Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri, Borno State.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Healthcare workers employed at Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri for at least 6 months.
2. Healthcare workers directly involved in patient care.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Adhoc staff working in the Primary Health Care centers.

Sample size determination

The sample size was calculated using the Cochran's formula;

$$n = Z_{\alpha}^2 p(1-p) / d^2$$

Where,

n = the minimum sample size required

Z_α = standard normal deviate corresponding to 95% at the level of significance (1.96)

P = proportion prevalence of burnout from previous study among health care workers in Abuja (11) which is 85% (0.85)

$d =$ desired level of precision usually at 5% (0.05)

$q =$ is complimentary probability of p ($1-p$) which is $1 - 0.85 = 0.15$

Therefore, $n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.85 \times 0.15 / (0.05)^2$

$n = 3.8416 \times 0.85 \times 0.15 / 0.0025$

$n = 195.9$

$n = 196$

Non-response of 10% was added.

Therefore, 10% of $n = 0.1 \times 196 = 19.6$ (non-response rate)

Adjusted sample size = $196 + 19.6 = 215.6$ which was approximated to 216.

Thus, the sample size calculated using the above formula is 216. The number was approximated to 272 to increase the research power.

Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling was used.

Stage I: Selection of Local Government Areas

There are 4 LGAs in Maiduguri, which are Jere, Maiduguri Metropolitan Council, Konduga and Mafa LGA's. Purposive sampling was used to select 2 LGAs which are Jere and Maiduguri Metropolitan Council.

Stage II: Selection of Wards

There are a total of 15 wards in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council (MMC) LGA and 12 wards in Jere LGA. A total of 25 Per cent of the wards was selected from each selected LGA using simple random sampling, resulting in the selection of 3 wards from Jere LGA, which are Maimusari, Mairi, and Old Maiduguri while 4 wards were selected from MMC, which include, Gwange I, Shewuri South, Bolori I, and Bolori II. Making a total of 7 wards selected for this study. This stage ensures geographical representation across the two LGAs.

Stage III: Selection of Primary Health Centers (PHCs)

From each of the 7 selected wards, one functional Primary Health Care centre (PHC) was selected using simple random sampling from the list of PHCs available in that ward. This will result in a total of 7 PHCs selected for this study.

Stage IV: Selection of Respondents

At each selected PHC, a list of eligible healthcare workers was obtained from the facility's duty roster and staff register. The number of respondents to be selected from each PHC was determined using proportionate allocation based on each facility staff size. Thereafter, systematic sampling was used to select individual respondents. The sampling interval (k) was calculated by dividing the total number of eligible staff by the number of respondents required at each facility. The first respondent was selected simple random selection, and subsequent respondents was selected at every k^{th} interval on the list.

Source of data and data collection instrument

The instrument used for data collection was a structured, self-administered questionnaire designed using Google Forms. It consisted of both closed ended and standardized questions, divided into four (4) main sections.

SECTION A: Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

SECTION B: Burnout assessment (Using the Adapted Oldenburg Burnout Inventory)

SECTION C: Coping mechanisms employed by respondents

SECTION D: Workplace factors contributing to burnout

To assess workplace burnout, the Oldenburg burnout inventory was adapted to suit the local healthcare centers and respondent profile while retaining the original scoring.

Method of Data Collection

Data were collected through direct physical administration of the Google Form questionnaire by the student researchers, who visited selected Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri Metropolitan Council and Jere LGAs of Borno state.

The data collection process lasted for a period 9th – 30th July (3 weeks) and all responses were automatically saved and compiled through the Google Forms platform for analysis.

Data Analysis

All Data collected was downloaded from the Google form platform, cleaned on Microsoft Excel (version 2020) and was thereafter coded and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, means, standard deviations) was used to summarize socio-demographics and burnout prevalence.

Inferential statistics (Chi-square test) was used to determine associations between burnout and selected variables with statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Research and Ethics Committee of Ministry of Health and Human services, Borno State (SHREC No. 91/2025). A formal letter of introduction was also presented to the heads of the selected PHC centers in Jere and MMC LGAs of Borno state, requesting permission to conduct the research.

Participation in the study was entirely voluntary and all respondents were informed about the purpose and objectives of the research before data collection. They were assured of confidentiality and anonymity and no identifying information was collected. Written informed consent was obtained from participant prior to administering the questionnaire. Respondents were also notified that they can withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences. The collected data were used strictly for academic purposes and access to the Google form dataset was restricted to only the student researchers and the supervisor.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study was conducted in the seven selected Primary Health Care centers, in Maiduguri, Borno State. A total of 272 questionnaires were administered, of which all were validly completed (response rate of 100%). The answers were coded and the results obtained were summarized, analyzed and presented in the table below.

TABLE 1
SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HEALTH CARE WORKERS IN
PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age(Years)		
18-24	41	15.1
25-34	122	44.9
35-44	67	24.6
>45	42	15.4
Total	272	100
Mean±S.D	33.85±9.03	
Gender		
Male	95	34.9
Female	177	65.1
Total	272	100
Marital Status		
Single	93	34.2
Married	156	57.4
Divorced	9	3.3
Widowed	14	5.1
Total	272	100
Cadre		
Nurse	55	20.2
CHO	26	9.6
CHEW	102	37.5
JCHEW	34	12.5
Laboratory Technician	55	20.2
Total	272	100

Table 1; The age distribution of respondents revealed that 44.9 Per cent were within the 25–34-year age group, this was followed by respondents aged 35–44 years (24.6%), while 15.4 Per cent were above 45 years and 15.1 Per cent were within the 18–24 years' group. This is in consistent with a study in Abuja among healthcare workers were majority of the respondents were within the age group of 31-40 years (65%), followed by 20-30 years (28%) (11).

About 177 (65.1%) of the respondents were female, while 95 (34.9%) were male. This is in consistent with the study conducted among healthcare workers in Abuja, Nigeria (11) where 67 (67%) were female and 33 (33%) were male.

Regarding marital status, 156 (57.4%) of the respondents were married, while 92 (34.2%) were single, 14 (5.1%) were widowed and 9 (3.3%) were divorced which is in consistent with a study in Enugu Nigeria (14) where a higher number of the respondent 124 (80%) were married while 31 (20%) were single. Similar a study among healthcare workers in Saudi Arabia (24) during the COVID 19 pandemic where 129 (61.7%) were married and 38 (18.2%) were single.

When examined by professional cadre, 102 (37.5%) of respondents were Community Health Extension Workers (CHEWs), this was followed by nurses and laboratory technicians, each constituting 55 (20.2%), Junior CHEWs made up 34 (12.5%), and there were no doctors among the respondents, this contrast the study in Delta (1) where Nurses (32.1%) and health assistants (50%) accounted for majority of the cadre of respondents out of the total Primary Healthcare workers in their study.

TABLE 1**CONTINUED. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HEALTH CARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025**

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
PHC Location		
Dalaram	49	18.0
Gwange	31	11.4
Maimusari	24	8.8
Mairi	32	11.8
Shuwari	48	17.6
Wulari	53	19.5
Yerwa	35	12.9
Total	272	100
Years of work experience		
1-2	53	19.5
3-5	77	28.3
6-10	74	27.2
>11	68	25
Total	272	100
Work days per week		
≤5	257	94.5
≥6	15	5.5
Total	272	100
Average working hours		
Per day		
<10	31	11.4
10-16	238	87.5
>16	3	1.1
Total	272	100

Table 1 (Continued); The distribution across the various Primary Health Care centers showed that Wulari (19.5%), Dalaram (18%), and Shuwari (17.6%) had the highest number of respondents, facilities like Yerwa (12.9%), Gwange (11.4%), Mairi (11.8%) and Maimusari (8.8%) had relatively fewer respondents.

In terms of years of professional experience, respondents were fairly distributed across categories. 77 (28.3%) had 3–5 years of experience, while 74 (27.2%) had 6–10 years. Those with more than 11 years of experience accounted for 68 (25%), and 53 (19.5%) had 1–2 years of experience. This is in contrast with a study among Nigerian medical doctors (15) in during the COVID-19 pandemic where lesser number of respondents 39 (15.5%) has 1-5 years of experience and 84 (33.5%) has 6-10 years of experience while 81 (32.3%) has 11-15 years of experience.

In with respect to working days per week, 94.5 Per cent respondents reported working 4–5 days weekly, only 5.5 Per cent worked 6–7 days. This is in contrast with a study in delta among HCW where almost half (42.1%) of the respondents worked for greater than 5 days per week (1).

Analysis of average working hours per day revealed that 87.5 Per cent worked between 10 to 16 hours daily, while 11.4 Per cent worked 7–9 hours and only 1.1 Per cent worked more than 16 hours per day, in contrast to the study conducted among PHC workers in Delta Nigeria where most (37.9%) of respondents worked for more than 8 hours per day (1).

TABLE 2**BURNOUT ASSESSMENT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTHCARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025**

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage(%)
I often feel tired before I arrive at work		
Strongly disagree	10	3.7
Disagree	48	17.6
Neutral	12	4.4
Agree	80	29.4
Strongly agree	122	44.9
Total	272	100
There are days when I feel tired before even starting work		
Strongly disagree	5	1.8
Disagree	46	16.9
Neutral	10	3.7
Agree	121	44.5
Strongly agree	90	33.1
Total	272	100
After work, I tend to need more time than usual to relax		
Strongly disagree	0	0.0
Disagree	11	4.0
Neutral	9	3.3
Agree	149	54.8
Strongly agree	103	37.9
Total	272	100

Table 2; The assessment of burnout among healthcare workers revealed that, 202 (74.3%) of the respondents indicated that they often feel tired before they even arrive at work. About 211 (77.6%) respondents reported that there are days when they feel tired even before starting work. 252 (92.7%) reported that after work they need more time than usual to relax.

TABLE 2a

CONTINUED. BURNOUT ASSESSMENT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTHCARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage(%)
I am able to handle the pressure of workload in the PHC facility		
Strongly disagree	19	7.0
Disagree	109	40.1
Neutral	23	8.3
Agree	103	37.9
Strongly agree	18	6.6
Total	272	100
I often feel emotionally drained by my job.		
Strongly disagree	1	0.4
Disagree	42	15.4
Neutral	16	5.9
Agree	135	49.6
Strongly agree	78	28.7
Total	272	100
I have enough energy after work to enjoy my personal life.		
Strongly disagree	55	20.2
Disagree	124	45.6
Neutral	15	5.5
Agree	67	24.6
Strongly agree	11	4.0
Total	272	100

Table 2a (continued); Shows that About 121 (44.5%) of the respondent felt able to handle the pressure of workload in their PHC facility. About 213 (78.3%) of the respondents acknowledged that they often feel emotionally drained by their job. About, 78 (28.6%) have enough time after work to enjoy their personal life.

TABLE 2b

CONTINUED. BURNOUT ASSESSMENT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTHCARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage(%)
I often feel worn out and tired after work		
Strongly disagree	2	0.7
Disagree	29	10.7
Neutral	15	5.5
Agree	143	52.6
Strongly agree	83	30.5
Total	272	100
I am able to manage my workload in the PHC effectively.		
Strongly disagree	26	9.6
Disagree	109	40.1
Neutral	28	10.3
Agree	103	37.9
Strongly agree	6	2.2
Total	272	100
I find new and interesting aspect in my work		
Strongly disagree	26	9.6
Disagree	77	28.3
Neutral	33	12.1
Agree	129	47.4
Strongly agree	7	2.6
Total	272	100

Table 2b (Continued); Shows that about 226 (83.1%) stated that they often feel worn out and tired after work. About 109 (40.1%) of the respondents agreed that they are able to manage their workload effectively. About 136 (47.4%) of the respondents reported that they find new and interesting aspects in their work.

TABLE 2c

CONTINUED. BURNOUT ASSESSMENT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTHCARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage(%)
Sometimes I feel sickened by my work tasks		
Strongly disagree	4	1.5
Disagree	41	15.15
Neutral	13	4.8
Agree	143	52.6
Strongly agree	71	26.1
Total	272	100
I frequently talk about my work in a negative way.		
Strongly disagree	21	7.7
Disagree	103	37.9
Neutral	36	13.2
Agree	99	36.4
Strongly agree	13	4.8
Total	272	100
I find it hard to stay motivated at my job		
Strongly disagree	5	1.8
Disagree	60	22.1
Neutral	17	6.3
Agree	165	60.7
Strongly agree	25	9.2
Total	272	100

Table 2c (continued); Shows that about 204 (78.7%) agree that they sometimes feel sickened by their work task, similarly 112 (41.2%) of the respondents admitted that they frequently talk about their work in a negative way. While 190 (69.9%) admitted that they find it hard to stay motivated at their job.

TABLE 2d

**CONTINUED. BURNOUT ASSESSMENT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN
PRIMARY HEALTHCARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025**

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage(%)
I feel unconcerned about my job performance.		
Strongly disagree	14	5.1
Disagree	138	50.7
Neutral	43	15.8
Agree	71	26.1
Strongly agree	6	2.2
Total	272	100
I feel more skeptical about whether my work contributes to anything.		
Strongly disagree	12	4.4
Disagree	126	46.3
Neutral	34	12.5
Agree	87	32.0
Strongly agree	13	4.8
Total	272	100
I find my work to be meaningless.		
Strongly disagree	62	22.8
Disagree	141	51.8
Neutral	25	9.2
Agree	38	14.0
Strongly agree	6	2.2
Total	272	100

Table 2d (Continued); Shows about 77 (28.3%) of the respondents reported feeling unconcerned about their job performance. 100 (36.8%) expressed skepticism about whether their work contributes to anything meaningful. while only about 44 (16.2%) of the respondents found their work to be meaningless.

TABLE 2e

CONTINUED. BURNOUT ASSESSMENT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTHCARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage(%)
This is the only kind of job I can see myself doing		
Strongly disagree	34	12.5
Disagree	126	46.3
Neutral	29	10.7
Agree	74	27.2
Strongly agree	9	3.3
Total	272	100
I feel more and more engaged in my work		
Strongly disagree	12	4.4
Disagree	74	27.2
Neutral	17	6.3
Agree	120	44.1
Strongly agree	49	18.0
Total	272	100

Table 2e (Continued); Shows that about 83 (30.5%) felt that this is the only kind of job they can see themselves doing. Finally, 169 (62.1%) expressed engagement in their work.

Figure 1: Burnout Level of Healthcare Workers in Primary Health Care centres in Maiduguri, Borno State. July, 2025

Figure 1; Shows the result obtained from the assessment of burnout and the distribution of burnout levels among 272 healthcare workers respondents in Primary healthcare centers across Jere and MMC LGAs, Borno state. Low burnout was reported in 29 healthcare workers, representing 10.7 Per cent of the respondents. Moderate burnout was recorded in 125 participants, which accounts for the highest proportion at 46.0 Per cent. High burnout was observed in 118 respondents, comprising 43.4 Per cent of the total respondents, giving a combined moderate and high burnout prevalence of 89.4 Per cent. The high burnout proportion alone (43.4%) is in contrast with a study conducted in Brazil which revealed a lower prevalence of burnout at 7 Per cent among PHC staff in Brazil (17). Likewise, a study in Belgium revealed burnout prevalence in European Union

countries at 10 Per cent and in non-European Union countries at 17 Per cent (18). However, the prevalence in this study is lower compared to another study conducted in India, where high burnout was reported in Iran at 52.9 Per cent (17). The combined burnout prevalence of 89.4 Per cent in this study is relatively higher compared to a study among healthcare workers in an Abuja private hospital, which revealed a prevalence of 85 Per cent (11). This is also consistent with a study done among nurses at a tertiary hospital in Enugu, which revealed a prevalence of 78.1 Per cent (14). Likewise, another study conducted among physicians in five tertiary hospitals revealed a burnout prevalence of 75.5 Per cent (16). The high burnout proportion in this study is similar to that reported in Delta State, where 45 Per cent burnout was recorded among health care workers (1). However, a study among healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals in Maiduguri reported 21.5 Per cent burnout which relatively lower than the burnout prevalence in this study (12).

TABLE 3

COPING MECHANISMS ADOPTED BY HEALTH CARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTERS TO MANAGE BURNOUT IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Talks to friends or colleagues about Stress		
Always	40	14.7
Often	67	24.6
Sometimes	111	40.8
Rarely	37	13.6
Never	17	6.3
Total	272	100
Find time to rest or take breaks during work		
Always	42	15.4
Often	79	29.0
Sometimes	109	40.1
Rarely	32	11.8
Never	10	3.7
Total	272	100
Engages in physical exercise or activity to relieve stress		
Always	26	9.6
Often	67	24.6
Sometimes	106	39.0
Rarely	59	21.7
Never	14	5.1
Total	272	100

Table 3; Shows the various coping mechanisms adopted by Primary healthcare workers to manage stress and prevent burnout in Primary healthcare centers in Jere and MMC LGAs, talking to friends or colleagues about stress was common, with 107 respondents (39.3%) doing so always or often, while 54 (19.9%) rarely or never used this approach. Finding time to rest or take breaks during work was practiced by 121 (44.5%), while 42 (15.4%) rarely or never engaged in this. Engaging in physical exercise or activity to relieve stress was less popular, with 93 (34.2%) practicing it always or often, and 73 (26.8%) rarely or never doing so. This was in contrast to a study among Nurses where 55 Per cent of the respondents reported over eating to be a major way to cope with burnout (14).

TABLE 3a
CONTINUED. COPING MECHANISMS ADOPTED BY HEALTH CARE WORKERS IN
PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTERS TO MANAGE BURNOUT IN MAIDUGURI,
BORNO STATE, JULY 2025.

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Pray, Meditate or use religious support to manage stress		
Always	75	27.6
Often	102	37.5
Sometimes	71	26.1
Rarely	21	7.7
Never	3	1.1
Total	272	100
Seeks help or counselling when feeling overwhelmed		
Always	26	9.6
Often	84	30.9
Sometimes	89	32.7
Rarely	51	18.8
Never	22	8.1
Total	272	100
Manage time better to reduce workload		
Always	34	12.5
Often	117	43.0
Sometimes	102	37.5
Rarely	18	6.6
Never	1	0.4
Total	272	100

Table 3a (Continued); Religious coping was the most frequent strategy, as 177 respondents (65.1%) reported that they always or often pray, meditate, or use religious support to manage stress, while only 24 (8.8%) rarely or never used it. which is in contrast with a study in Belgium were about 34 Per cent of the respondents use religious support to manage stress (18). Seeking help or counselling when overwhelmed was reported by 110 (40.4%), compared to 73 (26.9%) who rarely or never sought such help.

Similarly, about 151 (55.5%) often or always managed their time better to reduce workload, while just 19 (7%) rarely or never applied this strategy.

TABLE 3b
CONTINUED. COPING MECHANISMS ADOPTED BY HEALTH CARE WORKERS
IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTERS TO MANAGE BURNOUT IN MAIDUGURI,
BORNO STATE, JULY 2025.

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Distracts self with hobbies or entertainment after work		
Always	39	14.3
Often	100	36.8
Sometimes	91	33.5
Rarely	32	11.8
Never	10	3.7
Total	272	100
Uses humor or positive thinking to feel better		
Always	55	20.2
Often	78	28.7
Sometimes	103	37.9
Rarely	34	12.5
Never	2	0.7
Total	272	100
Uses substances to manage stress		
Always	1	0.4
Often	4	1.5
Sometimes	15	5.5
Rarely	37	13.6
Never	215	79.0
Total	272	100
Focuses on reason for choice of profession		
Always	91	33.5
Often	97	35.7
Sometimes	74	27.2
Rarely	8	2.9
Never	2	0.7
Total	272	100

Table 3b (Continued); Distraction through hobbies or entertainment after work was practiced by 139 (51.1%), whereas 42 (15.5%) rarely or never engaged in such activities. The use of humor or positive thinking was also common, with 133 respondents (48.9%) applying it always or often, while only 36 (13.2%) rarely or never used this strategy. In contrast, the use of substances to manage stress was very rare, with only 5 (1.8%) admitting to always or often using substances, while an overwhelming 252 (92.6%) rarely or never engaged in it. Finally, focusing on their reason for choosing the profession was reported by 188 respondents (69.2%) as an always or often coping strategy, while only 10 (3.6%) rarely or never practiced it.

TABLE 4**WORK RELATED FACTORS OF HEALTH CARE WORKERS ON PREVALENCE OF WORKPLACE BURNOUT IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTERS IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025.**

Variables	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
Supported by supervisor		
Yes	225	82.7
No	47	17.3
Total	272	100
Workload manageable		
Yes	217	79.8
No	55	20.2
Total	272	100
Considered Quitting due to stress		
Yes	109	40.1
No	163	59.9
Total	272	100
Access to mental Health support at work		
Yes	133	48.9
No	139	51.1
Total	272	100
Willingness to attend Mental Health Workshop		
Yes	235	86.4
No	37	13.6
Total	272	100

Table 4; Shows work related factors contributing to the prevalence of burnout among healthcare workers in Jere and MMC LGAs, Borno state. The result shows that 225 (82.7%) of respondents were supported by their supervisors, while 47(17.3%) were not. 217 (79.8%) of the respondents considered their workload is manageable, while 55 (20.2%) found it overwhelming. About 109 (40.1%) of the respondents considered quitting their job due to stress, while 163 (59.9%) did not consider quitting their job due to stress. Access to mental health support at work was almost evenly distributed with 51.1 Per cent having access and 48.9 Per cent lacking it. About 235 (86.4%) of healthcare workers expressed willingness to attend mental health workshops, while 37(13.6%) were not willing to attend a mental health workshop.

TABLE 5

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND LEVEL OF WORKPLACE BURNOUT AMONG PRIMARY HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025.

Variables	Low Burnout n (%)	Moderate Burnout n (%)	High Burnout n (%)	Total n (%)	Test statistic	P- value
Age(Years)						
18-24	5 (17.2)	20(16.0)	16(13.6)	41(100)	5.412 †	0.492
25-34	14(48.3)	49(39.2)	59(50.0)	122(100)		
35-44	4(13.8)	36(28.8)	27(22.9)	67(100)		
>45	6(20.7)	20(16.0)	16(13.6)	42(100)		
Gender						
Male	10(34.5)	42(33.6)	43(36.4)	95(100)	0.218 χ^2	0.897
Female	19(65.5)	83(66.4)	75(63.6)	177(100)		
Marital Status						
Single	15(51.7)	37(29.6)	41(34.7)	93(100)	6.550 †	0.327
Married	13(44.8)	79(63.2)	64(54.2)	156(100)		
Divorced	0(0.0)	4(3.2)	5(4.2)	9(100)		
Widowed	1(3.4)	5(4.0)	8(6.8)	14(100)		
Cadre						
Nurse	4(13.8)	26(20.8)	25(21.2)	55(100)	10.338 †	0.232
CHO	4(13.8)	7(5.6)	15(12.7)	26(100)		
CHEW	8(27.6)	52(41.6)	42(35.6)	102(100)		
JCHEW	4(13.4)	19(15.2)	11(9.3)	34(100)		
Laboratory Technician	9(31.0)	21(16.8)	25(21.2)	55(100)		

† Fischer-Freeman-Halton Exact test, χ^2 Pearson Chi-Square, * Statistically significant.

Table 5; presents the factors associated with socio-demographic variables and level of workplace burnout among primary healthcare workers in Primary Health Care centers in Maiduguri. Burnout was most prevalent among workers aged 25–34 years, with 59 reporting high burnout and 49 reporting moderate burnout, compared to lower frequencies in the 18–24, 35–44, and >45-year age groups. However, the association between age and burnout was not statistically significant ($p = 0.492$). In this study, the highest frequency of burnout occurred in the 25–34 age group. This finding is consistent with a study in Abuja, where younger middle-aged healthcare workers 31–40 years representing 58 (68.2%) reported higher levels of burnout (11).

Burnout levels were higher among female respondents with 75 recording high burnout, 83 with moderate burnout as compared to males, 43 and 42 with high and moderate burnout, respectively. Despite this, the relationship between gender and burnout was not statistically significant ($p = 0.897$) this is in contrast with a study in India among health care workers where the prevalence of personal and work-related burnout was significantly ($p < 0.01$) higher among females. (10)

With respect to marital status, married workers reported the highest cases of burnout which were 64 of the respondents followed by singles which were 41 and widowed were 8 while divorced were 5. The association, however, was not statistically significant ($p = 0.327$). This finding is consistent with a study conducted in Maiduguri among healthcare workers in tertiary hospitals (12), which revealed high burnout among married HCWs which represented 106 (72.6%) of the respondents. It also aligns with research in private hospitals in Abuja (11), where married healthcare workers 43 (50.6%) recorded higher

burnout levels as compared to singles 42 (40.9%). The higher prevalence of burnout among married respondents in this study may be attributed to the combined pressures of work and family responsibilities, which increase stress as compared to their single counterparts.

Analysis by cadre showed varying degrees of burnout, with Community Health extension workers (CHEWS) and Junior Community health extension workers (JCHEWs) appearing more affected. Nevertheless, this association was not statistically significant ($p = 0.232$).

TABLE 5a
CONTINUED. FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AND LEVEL OF WORKPLACE BURNOUT AMONG PRIMARY HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTRES IN MAIDUGURI, BORNO STATE, JULY 2025

Variables	Low Burnout n (%)	Moderate Burnout n (%)	High Burnout n (%)	Total n (%)	Test statistic	P- value
Years of work experience						
1-2	10(34.5)	29(23.2)	14(11.9)	53(100)	19.167 χ^2	0.004*
3-5	6(20.7)	25(20.0)	46(39.0)	77(100)		
6-10	5(17.2)	35(28.0)	34(28.8)	74(100)		
>11	8(27.6)	36(28.8)	24(20.3)	68(100)		
Work days per Week						
≤5	25(86.2)	117(93.6)	115(97.5)	257(100)	5.735 †	0.044*
>5	4(13.8)	8(6.4)	3(2.5)	15(100)		
Average of working hours						
1-9	4	11	16	31(100)	4.241 †	0.323
≥10	25	114	102	241(100)		

† Fischer-Freeman-Halton Exact test, χ^2 Pearson Chi-Square, * Statistically significant.

Table 5a (Continued); A significant relationship was observed between years of service and burnout ($p = 0.004$), with workers having 6–10 years of experience showing the highest proportion of high burnout. This is consistent with a cross sectional study among Nigerian medical doctors during COVID – 19 pandemics (15) where a significant relationship ($p = 0.035$) was found between burnout and years of work experience.

As regards work days per week, there is significant relationship between burnout.

Finally, longer working hours (≥ 10 per day) were associated with a higher prevalence of burnout (102 high cases) compared to those working 1–9 hours daily. However, the association was not statistically significant ($p = 0.323$).

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Burnout recognized by the WHO as an occupational phenomenon, is a major challenge in healthcare systems, especially among healthcare workers exposed to long-term stress and high job demands. It leads to physical and emotional exhaustion, reduced productivity, absenteeism, poor interpersonal relations, and compromised patient care. Globally, burnout prevalence is high, worsened by COVID-19, with reports ranging from 27Per cent to 85Per cent depending on setting.

In Nigeria, particularly in conflict-affected Borno State, the problem is severe due to insecurity, destruction of health facilities, staff shortages, inadequate supplies, and overstretched workloads. Studies reveal significant burnout rates among Nigerian healthcare workers, including in Maiduguri. Burnout not only threatens HCWs' mental and physical health but also contributes to errors, attrition, and poor service delivery.

Burnout is a pressing public health concern causing psychological, occupational, and systemic consequences. In Borno State, PHC workers face compounded risks due to insecurity and resource constraints.

This study investigates the prevalence of workplace burnout among healthcare workers in Maiduguri's Primary Health Care centers. It examines levels of burnout, coping mechanism and the influence of work-related and socio-demographic factors to inform interventions that enhance staff well-being and healthcare delivery.

Based on the findings from this study, the following summaries were made:

1. Most PHC workers in Maiduguri are young (25–34 years) with a Mean age of 33.85, female (65.1%), and married (57.4%), mainly nurses and community health workers, with 3–10 years' experience. They typically work 4–5 days a week for 10–16 hours per day, spread across all PHC locations.
2. Overall, 89.4 Per cent of PHC workers experienced burnout (46% moderate, 43.4% high), while only 10.7 Per cent reported low burnout.
3. Most healthcare workers cope with stress through talking to colleagues (40.8%), taking breaks (40.1%), exercising (39%), and religious support (65.1%), while fewer use counseling (40.5%). Motivation comes mainly from their reason for choosing the profession (79%). Substance use was very rare (1.8%).
4. Most healthcare workers feel supported by their supervisors (82.7%) and find their workload manageable (79.8%). Despite this, 40.1 Per cent have considered quitting due to stress. About 48.9 Per cent have access to mental health support, and a high 86.4 Per cent are willing to attend mental health workshops.
5. Burnout is highest among 25–34-year-olds (moderate 39.2%, high 50%) and staff working long hours (≥ 10 hours/day), while younger staff and those working ≤ 5 days/week experience lower burnout. Burnout was significantly associated with years of work experience ($p=0.004$) and number of workdays per week ($p=0.044$), but not with age, gender, cadre and marital status.

Conclusion

Burnout among PHC workers in Maiduguri is relatively high, with 46% and 43.4% experiencing moderate and high burnout respectively. This study suggests the need for policy intervention from the health authorities and the state with regards to improving staff welfare, employing more staffs and introducing mental health interventions to reduce workplace burnout among PHC healthcare workers in Maiduguri, Borno State.

Recommendations

1. The State ministry of Health and Human resources through the primary health care management board should ensure that the PHC facilities should be in line with concept of PHC Under -One- Roof and should be adequately staffed with improve staff welfare and make provisions for incentives.
2. The in charge or manager in the various PHC Centers should review the working hours per day, introduce flexible shifts and be given extra allowance for any extra work shift taken.
3. The federal government through the National Primary Healthcare Development Agency (NPHCDA) should provide adequate funding and equipment for better running of health care services in the Primary health care centers especially in insecurity and low resource setting like Borno state.
4. The Federal government should ensure the revitalization of the non-functional PHC centers in the remaining two LGAs in Maiduguri (Konduga and Mafa LGA) by curbing the issues of insecurity in the area due to Boko Haram insurgency.

5. The ministry of health and human resources in collaboration with local government authorities, primary health care management and supported by partner organization should introduce regular mental health interventions and awareness programs in PHC facilities, this should include stress management workshops to reduce burnout among healthcare workers.

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APPENDIX A
QUESTIONNAIRE

**ASSESSMENT OF WORKPLACE BURNOUT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN
PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTERS IN MAIDUGURI BORNO STATE.**

Section A: Socio-Demographic Data

Please fill in or tick where appropriate.

Name/Location of PHC: _____

1. How old are you? _____
2. What is your Gender? Male Female
3. What is your Marital Status? Single Married Divorced Widowed
4. What is your Cadre? Doctor Nurse CHO CHEW JCHEW Lab Technician Other: _____
5. What is your Years of Work Experience? _____
6. What is your Number of Workdays per Week? _____
7. What is your Average Working Hours per Day? _____

Section B: Burnout Assessment (Adapted Oldenburg Burnout Inventory)

Please indicate how much you agree with each statement using the following scale:

1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

I. Exhaustion

8. I often feel tired before I arrive at work.

1 2 3 4 5

9. There are days when I feel tired before even starting work.

1 2 3 4 5

10. After work, I tend to need more time than usual to relax.

1 2 3 4 5

11. I am able to handle the pressure of work in the PHC facility. (*positive)

1 2 3 4 5

12. I often feel emotionally drained by my work.

1 2 3 4 5

13. I have enough energy after work to enjoy my personal life. (*positive)

1 2 3 4 5

14. I often feel worn out and weary after work

1 2 3 4 5

15. I am able to manage my workload effectively (*positive)

1 2 3 4 5

II. Disengagement

16. I find new and interesting aspects in my work at the PHC (*positive)

1 2 3 4 5

17. Sometimes I feel sickened by my work tasks.

1 2 3 4 5

18. I frequently talk about my work in a negative way.

1 2 3 4 5

19. I find it hard to stay motivated at my job.

1 2 3 4 5

20. I feel indifferent about my job performance.

1 2 3 4 5

21. I feel more cynical about whether my work contributes to anything.

1 2 3 4 5

22. I find my work to be meaningless.

1 2 3 4 5

23. This is the only kind of job I can see myself doing. (*positive)

1 2 3 4 5

24. I feel more and more engaged in my work. (*positive)

1 2 3 4 5

Section C: Additional Work-Related Factors

25. Do you feel supported by your supervisor? Yes No
26. Do you feel your workload is manageable? Yes No
27. Have you ever considered quitting your job due to stress? Yes No
28. Do you have access to mental health support at work? Yes No
29. Would you be willing to attend a stress management workshop? Yes No

Section D: Coping Mechanisms

Please indicate how often you use the following strategies to cope with stress or burnout at work.

1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Always

30. I talk to friends or colleagues about my stress.

1 2 3 4 5

31. I try to find time to rest or take breaks during work.

1 2 3 4 5

32. I engage in physical exercise or activity to relieve stress.

1 2 3 4 5

33. I pray, meditate, or use spiritual/religious support.

1 2 3 4 5

34. I seek help or counseling when I feel overwhelmed.

1 2 3 4 5

35. I try to manage my time better to reduce workload.

1 2 3 4 5

36. I use humor or positive thinking to feel better.

1 2 3 4 5

37. I distract myself with hobbies or entertainment after work.

1 2 3 4 5

38. I use substances (alcohol, pills, etc.) to manage stress.

1 2 3 4 5

39. I focus on the reasons I chose this profession.

1 2 3 4 5

40. Please describe any other ways you cope with work-related stress or burnout:

Date _____ Signature/Thumbprint of Respondent _____

Interviewer Code _____ Serial no _____

Time Interview Starts _____ Time Interview End _____

Thank you for accepting to Participate.

For Further Enquiries, Contact 09034039650

APPENDIX B
INFORMED CONSENT

Dear Respondent,

We are final year medical students of the College of Medical Sciences, University of Maiduguri conducting a final year Community Medicine project on "Prevalence of Workplace Burnout among Healthcare Workers in Primary Health Centers in Jere and MMC LGAs, Maiduguri, Borno State." This research is purely for academic purposes, and your participation is entirely voluntary.

The questionnaires will evaluate two key components of workplace burnout, Exhaustion which is the physical and emotional fatigue caused by work and Disengagement which is the loss of interest, motivation, or emotional distance from work. It also evaluates the workplace related factors and the coping strategies used by healthcare workers to manage stress and burnout in the primary health care centers.

There are no known risks associated with participating, and your responses will be kept strictly confidential and anonymous. You may choose not to answer any question or to withdraw at any time.

Your honest and complete answers will contribute greatly to the quality of this research. Thank you for your cooperation.

Please tick the box to indicate your agreement:

- [] I have read and understood the purpose of this study.
- [] I voluntarily agree to participate in this research.
- [] I understand that I can withdraw at any time without any consequence.

Signature: _____ Date: _____

APPENDIX C
ETHICAL CLEARANCE

MINISTRY OF HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES

*All Correspondence to be addressed to:
The Honourable Commissioner*

Musa Usman Secretariat Complex,
P.M.B. 1044,
Maiduguri, Borno State.
info@moh.bo.gov.ng

Our Ref: _____
Your Ref: _____

SHREC No. 91/2025

RE: PREVALENCE OF WORKPLACE BURNOUT AMONG HEALTHCARE WORKERS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CENTRES IN JERE AND MAIDUGURI METROPOLITAN COUNCIL LGAS, BORNO STATE

Research Ethics Committee assigned No: 91/2025

Name Investigators: BONIFACE UGBEDE OGIRI, HARUNA ZAKKA, MUHAMMAD BELLO YUSUF, GAUIS WURANI JOSHUA, KHADIJA MUHAMMAD SHUWA, AISHA MUNTAQA ABUBAKAR and ALIYU PHILIP SHALLANQWA

Address of investigator: Department of Community Medicine, College of Medical Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Nigeria.

Date of receipt of valid application: 3rd July, 2025
Date when final determination of research was made: 8th July, 2025

NOTICE OF RESEARCH EXEMPTION

This is to inform you that the activity described in the submitted protocol/documents have been reviewed and the State Health Research Ethics Committee has determined that, according to the National Code for Health Research Ethics, the activity described therein meets the criteria for exemption and is therefore granted provisional approval as exempt from SHREC.

2. The State Health Research Ethics requires you to comply with all institutional guidelines, rules, and regulations and with the tenets of the Code. You are also expected to share your findings on the study with the State for further dissemination.

Dr. Aliyu Shettima
Chairman
State Health Research Ethics Committee

APPENDIX D
CALCULATION OF SAMPLE INTERVAL

To calculate for proportion allocation for each PHC;

$$n_i = N_i / N \times n$$

Where,

n_i = Sample size to be selected from each PHC

N_i = Population size of the group (number of staff in that PHC)

N = total population size (all staff in all selected PHCs combined)

n = total sample size for the study

To calculate for Sample interval;

$$k = N/n$$

Where; N = number of staff in each PHC, n = number required per PHC

- | | | |
|------------------|----------------------------|------------------------------|
| 1. Dalaram PHC | = $73/406 \times 272 = 49$ | ($k = 73/49 = 1.5 \sim 2$) |
| 2. Gwange PHC | = $46/406 \times 272 = 31$ | ($k = 46/31 = 1.5 \sim 2$) |
| 3. Maimusari PHC | = $36/406 \times 272 = 24$ | ($k = 36/24 = 1.5 \sim 2$) |
| 4. Mairi PHC | = $48/406 \times 272 = 32$ | ($k = 48/32 = 1.5 \sim 2$) |
| 5. Shuwari PHC | = $72/406 \times 272 = 48$ | ($k = 72/48 = 1.5 \sim 2$) |
| 6. Wulari PHC | = $79/406 \times 272 = 53$ | ($k = 79/53 = 1.5 \sim 2$) |
| 7. Yerwa PHC | = $52/406 \times 272 = 35$ | ($k = 52/35 = 1.5 \sim 2$) |